

Reality Checks for a Distributional Assumption: The Case of “Benford’s Law”

William M. Goodman¹

¹University of Ontario Institute of Technology, 2000 Simcoe St. N., Oshawa, ON L1H 7K4

Abstract

In recent years, many articles have promoted uses for “Benford’s Law,” claimed to identify a nearly ubiquitous distribution pattern for the frequencies of first digits of numbers in many data sets. Detecting fraud in financial and scientific data is a suggested application. Like the Normal and Chi-square distributions, Benford’s appears to offer an appealingly clear-cut, mathematically tractable, and widely applicable tool. However, similar to those other models, writers may “assume” the model meets all the assumptions needed for hypothesis testing, without properly examining whether those conditions hold. This paper examines a diverse set of real-world data sets to demonstrate that while Benford’s-like patterns are indeed common, Benford’s per se is not a unique and universal template for all cases of interest to fraud investigators. This reminds us of how, in general, distributional assumptions can sometimes be overlooked or fail to be critically questioned.

Key Words: Benford’s Law, Statistical Assumptions, Distributional Assumptions, Audits, Statistical Literacy

1. Introduction to the Assumptions Issue and the Case

When testing hypotheses in applied settings, it is quite common to take advantage of familiar techniques that presume underlying distributions for the data, such as the normal, binomial, chi-square, or Poisson, which are mathematically well-specified and established in the literature. If the model’s assumptions apply, the strategy has clear advantages. Its calculation methods for estimates, significance and power are well known, and are therefore easy to look up if necessary, and may in fact be implemented in software. There is also the advantage that compared to using less familiar techniques, one’s findings based on accepted methods will seem easier to explain and justify to clients and/or journal editors and reviewers.

A disadvantage of ‘tried and true’ models is that, drawn by their benefits and familiarity, researchers may forget to ensure (or even enquire) whether the required conditions are met. In that case, the resulting graphs, output data, and conclusions may be misleading. How often, for example, are t tests applied for small samples, without checking or acknowledging if the population is highly skewed? Or linear regression applied when the variance for the error term can be shown to be highly non-constant?

Occasionally, new entrants may be added to this list of testing methods, becoming accepted enough in their domains that, if caution is forgotten, writers and readers may

tend to feel a comfort level without bothering too much about underlying assumptions. This may be happening now with hypothesis testing based on so-called “Benford’s Law,” promoted by many as a way to detect evidence of fraud and error in certain datasets. Watching this method’s emergence, and how it is being applied (assisted by modern advances in computer power to analyze large datasets), can provide a useful case study; it is a cautionary tale for ways distributional assumptions sometimes start getting overlooked or—perhaps more serious for this technique—not critically questioned.

2. Some Background and Literature on Benford’s Law, and its Proposed Application

2.1 The Curious Phenomenon

The phenomenon now known as Benford’s Law (BL) was actually first discovered by astronomer Simon Newcomb over a century ago, who presented it in the *American Journal of Mathematics* as a note on “the frequency of use of the different digits in natural numbers” (Newcomb, 1881). It was rediscovered by physicist Frank Benford, who published it as the “law of anomalous numbers” (Benford, 1938). Both observed that in many numeric datasets, the distribution of their first digit proportions (i.e., of the proportions of numbers in each dataset beginning with 1’s versus 2’s versus 3’s, and so on) is not uniform, as might be expected, but rather seems to follow a generalizable pattern.

In their times Newcomb and Benford would both have used tables of logarithms (in book format) as a tool to help with calculations involving multiplication and powers. Both, independently, happened to notice that pages near the front of these books were more worn than pages near the end. This suggested that for some reason there were more numbers to be looked up near the front (e.g., starting with the digits 1, 2, or 3) than numbers to be looked up near the back (starting with 7, 8, or 9).

Without too much effort, datasets can be easily found that appear to support this observation. Table 1 is based on 2012 data for housing unit counts estimated by county in Washington State.¹ The first-digit proportions expected by BL are shown in the second column. In this sample ($n = 326$, blanks and 0’s excluded), we see that the actual first-digit proportions in the fourth column are quite close to the expected proportions.

Table 1: BL-expected Versus Actual Distributions of First Digit Proportions for Numbers of Housing Units in Counties of Washington State

<i>First Digit</i>	<i>BL-Expected Proportions</i>	<i>Actual Frequencies for the First Digits</i>	<i>Actual Proportions for the First Digits</i>
1	0.301030	97	0.297546
2	0.176091	59	0.180982
3	0.124939	38	0.116564
4	0.096910	34	0.104294
5	0.079181	28	0.085890
6	0.066947	15	0.046012
7	0.057992	22	0.067485
8	0.051153	18	0.055215
9	0.045757	15	0.046012

¹ Raw data sources used for this paper are listed in Table 2, following the References section.

To give a sense of how these proportions look in the original raw data, Figure 1 displays a small subset of the housing units sample. Observe how many more numbers start with 1's than with 9's.

8590	4017	2608	1756	467	54262	2687	4339
1557	241	91	3475	1851	793	213	126
94894	39300	53	16688	1287	2232	728	168

Figure 1: Numbers of Housing Units in Counties of Washington State, 2012. (Subset from the full sample.)

The expected proportions, displayed in Table 1, can be derived from this formula:

$$(1) \quad \text{Prob}(D_1 = d_1) = \text{Log}_{\text{base}}(1 + 1/d_1), \text{ for all } d_1 = 1, 2, \dots, (\text{base}-1)$$

where D_1 refers to the first significant digit of a number in the dataset, and base refers the base of the number system in use. For our base 10 number system, the possible first significant digits range from 1 to $(10-1) = 9$. Hence, the expected proportion of numbers in the dataset that will start with 2, for example, will be $\text{Log}_{\text{base}10}(1+1/2) = 0.17609$.

Benford's Law is said to be base invariant and scale invariant. The former means that if the raw data are converted to another number system, Formula 1 still applies, and essentially the same distribution shape is expected. Scale invariance means that if units are converted from, say, from meters to miles, or from dollars (US) to dollars (Canadian), then the same basic patterns should apply as well. A non-technical account on why these properties might apply is found in Fewster (2009).

(A first reality check, however, is in order: The above-mentioned "equivalences" are perfect only at an abstract level, and can break down especially for smaller samples. The problem is analogous to the impact of revising class limits when constructing frequency distribution tables or histograms: The distributions' apparent shapes may change depending on where specific data values happen to fall in relation to the revised class boundaries. In the same way, in a relatively small dataset, a batch of conversions from, for example, numbers close to 100 U.S. dollars to "equivalent" numbers close to 96 Canadian dollars could alter the observed ratio of first-digit 1's to first-digit 9's.)

Benford's Law can also be extended to other digits as well as the first. Benford himself calculated *second*-digit proportions for the numbers in a dataset. (For example, "73972" and "131" both share the same second digit 3.) Berger and Hill (2011a, p. 3) describe how to calculate not just the expected proportions of digits within a set of numbers, for any digit position, but also calculate joint distributions for any combinations of digit positions. All these patterns will skew to the right, but Figure 2 illustrates that the distributions for different digit positions really become quite uniform by the third digit.

Figure 2: BL-Expected Distributions of Proportions for Specific First, Second, Third, and Fourth Digits of Numbers in a Dataset

As for why Benford’s Law seems to work, there has certainly been much conjecture. A classic reference is T.P. Hill’s paper in *Statistical Science* “A Statistical Derivation of the Significant-Digit Law” (1995) His previously cited paper with A. Berger in *Probability Surveys* (Berger & Hill, 2011a) investigates relationships between invariant properties of BL-type patterns and the properties of numbers generally, as well as various mathematical sequences. Common explanations play on the idea that numbers generated by multiplications and combinations (such as expense amounts—tending to have been based on prices times quantities) are likely to exhibit roughly logarithmic distributions (Durtschi, Hillison, & Pacini, 2004); and, in turn, numbers with a logarithmic distribution will tend towards having BL-first-digit distributions. Some alternative explanations are provided by Scott and Fasli (2001), Rodriguez (2009), and Gauvrit and Delahaye (2009).

In short, the evidence suggests that Benford’s Law is not something merely unfathomable. Yet even Berger and Hill (2011b) acknowledge that the law has *not* been precisely derived as yet, nor do we fully understand why some Benford-suitable² datasets actually conform to it, and others do not. This disclaimer is highly relevant for those who propose to *apply* Benford’s law. If a dataset of interest ‘fails’ to conform to the law in a test, we cannot know whether, due to confounders, this may possibly have been expected for this particular type of case.

2.2 The Proposed Application of Benford’s Law

A frequent writer on Benford’s Law, M. J. Nigrini, captures the confidence that many now place on this phenomenon to become the basis for fraud- and error-seeking hypothesis testing. “Benford’s law,” he writes, “is used to determine *the normal level* of number duplication in data sets” (Nigrini, 1999). (Emphasis added.) The implication is

² The concept of “Benford-Suitability” will be discussed in Section 2.3

that if somebody's set of accounting records, or of election vote counts, or data from an experimental trial do not conform sufficiently, then perhaps "non-normal" tampering or error of some sort has occurred.

This is a very serious application, given the impact that conclusions on these matters could have on people's reputations, or even jobs. We have seen in Section 2.1 some evidence that Benford's describes a real, and mathematically tractable distribution of some sort. But much the same can be said of the normal and Poisson distributions; yet it does not follow that these are always the appropriate models to be applied.

In the literature, discussions of possible Benford-testing applications often include analytical looks at pre-existing data, and conclusions can range from the cautious to the almost sensational. The latter include catchy newspaper stories like "...Scholar uses math to foil financial fraud" (Berton, 1995), which might have been excluded from serious discussion—except surprising numbers of reference chains (purporting to point to real-world use of BL by auditors) seem to lead back to such accounts.

On the more cautious side is Buyse *et al.*'s paper on detecting fraud in clinical trials (1999). These authors see BL tests as just part of a suite of approaches that can be used, with various tests having particular strengths depending on the nature of the fraud.

Most of the application-oriented papers try for a balance. On the one hand, they often start with a provocative title like "Root Out Financial Deception" (Albrecht & Albrecht, 2002), or "Breaking the (Benford's) Law: Statistical Fraud Detection in Campaign Finance" (Cho & Gaines, 2007); and they seem to accept—cautiously—that the BL model can be valid for testing. But on the other hand, they are cognizant of various confounders and risks of Type I and Type II error, and recognize that the method should not be interpreted mechanically, but one should consider models for how the fraud occurred (Deckert, Myagkov, & Ordeshook, 2011).

2.3 Benford Suitability

No one claims that Benford distributions are exhibited by numbers in all numeric datasets. The formula and tables in Section 2.1 only apply for datasets of certain types. An often-cited list of features to look for, or avoid, if seeking a BL-conforming dataset, is provided by Durtschi *et al.* (2004). This list can be condensed to the following. A dataset could be called *Benford-suitable* if:

- a. The dataset is large.
- b. Its values span several orders of magnitude.
- c. The values in the dataset have a positively skewed distribution.
- d. The dataset is not comprised of numbers that are assigned, or firm-specific, or directly influenced by human intentions.

Guideline (a) really pertains to sampling; it is not a rule about what makes a dataset "inherently" BL-suitable. If a sample is too small, there may be insufficient power to meaningfully detect or confirm conformance with the law. For a small sample of size 20, for instance, even a couple more numbers starting with digit 1 than expected, would change the apparent proportions, but one could not reach valid conclusions.

Guideline (b), requiring a large span of data values, can also be related to sampling. Even if the first digits for a company's cash receipts are inherently BL distributed, if the

numbers in certain day's sample only range from \$20 to \$500, then occurrences of first digit 1 would be underrepresented in the sample: 1's could only be observed in the 100's range, while, for example, first digit 3 gets two 'opportunities' to be observed--in the 30's and the 300's. If a printer glitch or other confounding factor had deleted receipt amounts outside a certain range, then the "real underlying" BL pattern may be missed.

On the other hand, guideline (b) can sometimes be a variant of guideline (d) (discussed below). This could occur if the orders-of-magnitude limitations reflect man-made constraints, such as minimum purchase amounts or transaction limits for debit-card purchases

Guideline (c), which looks for positively skewed distributions of numbers, may follow from how (per Section 2.1) BL distributions may be generated. Numbers derived by a process of combinations or multiplications can tend towards logarithmic-shaped distributions, having extended right tails. These distributions, in turn, are more likely than others to exhibit the BL-first-digit patterns

Guideline (d) complements (c): If numbers are *not* generated by a potentially suitable process, but are merely assigned, based on human intentions and considerations, then they are not likely to exhibit the BL patterns. Examples include: phone numbers, assigned in arbitrarily number sequences; or "bonus points" on purchases, accumulated at pre-set amounts; or withdrawal amounts at ATMs (automated teller machines), at quantities deemed "convenient" and below the customer's withdrawal limits.

3. Assumptions—and Reality Checks

Section 2.2 discusses many authors' proposals for using Benford's Law as a basis for hypothesis testing--specifically as a tool to uncover error and fraud in numeric datasets. We have described the phenomenon that "Benford's Law" refers to, and some of its basics. We can now start the case study, per se, for this paper. What assumptions are being made by those who would use BL for such hypothesis tests? And do those assumptions stand up to analysis?

3.1 Assumption 1: That individual, Benford-suitable datasets generally, also, conform to Benford's Law (by appropriate measurements of conformance).

Proposed BL applications take individual data sets from Benford-suitable domains such as financial records, medical trial results, and so on, and compare their first-digit distributions to those expected by Benford's Law. So long as the data are Benford-suitable, it is presumed that--barring fraud or data-entry mistakes or occasional Type I testing errors--the dataset *should also* be Benford conforming (according to appropriate measurement instruments). Otherwise, if it is common for datasets to be Benford-suitable, but to not conform beyond that, then nothing would follow from a BL-based test.

The actual evidence, however, does not support that Benford-suitable datasets necessarily also exhibit BL-expected, first digit distributions, upon measurement. This is illustrated in Figure 3, showing four distributions taken from a larger set of 40 cases collected by the author. While some of the cases conform nicely to Benford's, others do not. Neither result appears unusual.

Figure 3: Distributions of First Digits for Four Benford-Suitable Datasets

3.2 Assumption 2: That “representative samples” from the population of Benford-suitable datasets are well-defined.

BL-based hypothesis tests are not randomly controlled. Generally, datasets of interest (such as financial reports) pre-exist. The test model (per Assumption 1) seems to be: Compare the dataset at hand with datasets we might expect to have obtained if it we had taken true, representative samples from the population of Benford-suitable datasets. But these “representative samples” are not well defined.

First, the population of all Benford-suitable datasets is infinite. It includes every set of Benford-suitable numbers in any context, past, present, or future, that might ever be generated. What could serve as the sampling frame? Also: Does the population being sampled consist of numbers *as actually recorded* (as implied in suitability guideline (a)) or to magnitudes *as generated* (as implied in guideline (c))—regardless of whether anyone records them?

It is also not clear if there is only one population to be sampled from, or many. (For more on this, see Section 3.3.) Benford’s original paper includes 20 samples of apparently suitable datasets. But it is an odd combination of sets, ranging from values for areas of rivers and for costs of concrete, to mathematical series like “ $n^1 \dots n^8, n!$ ”. Some of his “samples” are not from one source domain at all, but from numbers drawn indirectly from diverse and unrelated sources, such as numbers happening to appear in Readers Digest or newspaper articles—on presumably many topics. Do such sets belong in the same population as the one whose sampling distribution might ground the testing on someone’s financial records? Moreover, if a column of source data includes some numbers that are totals or averages of other numbers in the same column (as does happen), is the result the same sample as the source data *without* those aggregates (but

needing cleaning), or it a brand new sample, and would every variant that includes extra subtotals be additional samples?

3.3 Assumption 3: That the “Convergence” of Benford-suitable datasets solves the problems arising from Assumptions 1 and 2.

3.3.1 The “convergence” phenomenon

Some authors have realized that, as noted above, it is simply not the case that all Benford-suitable datasets are automatically likely to be closely Benford-conforming, upon measurement. But these authors are not worried. Discussing what Berger and Hill (2011a) later call ‘almost sure convergence,’ Hill writes (1998): “If distributions are selected at random (in any “unbiased” way) and random samples are taken from each of those distributions, then the significant-digit frequencies of the combined sample will converge to Benford’s distribution, even though the individual distributions selected may not closely follow the law”. Berger and Hill later make the analogy with the Central Limit Theorem, in the sense that while individual samples’ means may differ from the true population mean, nonetheless, collectively all the samples’ means *center around* the true mean. This seems to also address objections to Benford’s mixtures-type examples (e.g., drawing numbers arbitrarily from newspaper articles); in fact, such mixtures now become the paradigm for the mixing and matching of samples to get the convergence effect.

The evidence is certainly highly supportive of Hill’s convergence model. It is not even necessary to pre-mix the individual samples in any way, as in Benford’s collection of numbers. To the contrary, Figure 4 is based on data from 40 samples collected by the author (listed in Table 2, at the end) which were intentionally as unmixed, cleaned, and independent as possible. (For example, one sample was 24 years of daily stock trading volumes; another was counts of telephone lines in use, by country; another was U.S. Civil War casualties, by battle; and so on.) Several of the dataset topics utilized were first suggested by Aldous and Phan (2010).

Figure 4: “Convergence” of Datasets’ First-Digit Proportions to BL-Expected Values

Lined up over each digit in the X axis, in Figure 4, is a vertical boxplot. This answers, in the form of a distribution, the question: What proportions of numbers, in each of the 40, respective datasets, begin with the corresponding digit on the X axis? For example, for the proportions of datasets beginning with 1, the median value is about 0.30; the first quartile is a bit above 0.25, and we see that one dataset has only 0.1 of its numbers beginning with 1; and so on. Notice that the median proportions of first-digit occurrences for each digit on the X axis are impressively very close to the BL-expected proportions.

For explanations of this convergence, I defer to the extensive treatment by mathematicians Berger and Hill (2011a). Certainly, it does seem confirmed that the phenomenon occurs.

3.3.2 Convergence does not support Assumption 3

Although the analogy of the Central Limit Theorem (CLT) may help to explain Figure 4, it cannot justify hypothesis testing based on Benford's Law. CLT says that the means of samples taken from a population will, collectively, tend to be centered on the true mean for the population. Similarly, it would appear, BL-convergence says that first-digit distributions of sampled datasets {implied: taken from a population} will, collectively, tend to be centered on the true first-digit distributions {for the population}. This does seem parallel. However, what population is meant? The only (implied) population from which all the collected, BL-suitable datasets are drawn is the amorphous and infinite population discussed in Section 3.2: Namely, the population of all possible BL-suitable datasets. How can *that* population be the standard for testing patterns expected in *specific* datasets collected from very *specific* domains?

To use in hypothesis tests the converged population that is centered on the BL-expected values commits the *aggregation fallacy*. This fallacy arises when comparing measures that are at different levels of aggregation. Figure 5 shows a simple example.

Figure 5: Potential for Aggregation Fallacy if Company Types are Ignored

The figure supposes there are five types of companies. To simplify, assume that (a) all the companies' financial datasets contain identical numbers of numeric entries, and (b) there are exactly 100 companies of each type. The figure shows that, for some reason, companies of Type A tend to have only 19% of the numbers in their financial records starting with the digit 1; whereas for companies of Type E, over 40% of numbers in their records start with the digit 1; and so on. Yet, if all 500 companies' records are aggregated, the *overall* proportion of numbers starting with the digit 1 is 30%.

In this case, if one audits the records of a "Type A" company, but ignores the apparent impact of the variable "Type" on the first-digit proportions, then (if using, say, a binomial test) the A company's 19% proportion of first-digit-1's is significantly different from the aggregate population proportion of 30%. Can we conclude from this test that something is wrong or unusual with that A company's data? Clearly, in this example, that would be a mistaken conclusion.

Convergence, in other words cannot be used to bypass Assumption 1. Assumption 3 seems at first to smooth out unexplained differences among specific, BL-suitable datasets. But in the final regard, if we wish to test a specific dataset from a specific domain, we still need to know if *this* sample belongs, for some reason, to a sub-group that may be non-BL-conforming.

3.4 Assumption 4: Only the Center is Important for Modeling the Sampling Distribution

Despite the concerns expressed in Section 3.3, it is conceivable that in the population of BL-suitable datasets, there are *no* valid, systematic subdivisions of a sort that could lead to the Aggregation Fallacy. If that is the case (which is an unknown), then Convergence would really tell us the expected center of Benford-conforming distributions, and thus provide *part* of a model for hypothesis testing: namely, the center. But what would be the error term?

In the applied BL literature, attempts to actually measure the error term for the null model for BL-based hypothesis testing, are hard to find. Some authors working with simulations, such as Bhattacharya, Kumar, & Smarandache (2005) have tried to consider the error. But even those such as Scott and Fasli (2001) who have tried to compile empirical data, are focused on using it to confirm or disconfirm BL itself. They are not asking the question: If one does use BL for testing, then what would be the appropriate magnitude for the standard error?

The error term for a test is generally estimated by a model for the "sampling distribution" of the measure of interest, with empirical inputs required. If we are testing for the mean, for example, and have some estimate for the population variance (σ^2), then we might estimate the standard error as σ/\sqrt{n} . This gives an idea of how far sample means drawn from that population might tend to vary from the true population mean, without anything being unusual.

If the conformance model is really correct with regard to the BL-population center, it does not tell us the population variance. (The following comments apply whether testing, separately, the conformance of each possible first digit (or other-digit) to its BL-expected proportions, or for testing *overall* conformance of a dataset to the expected distribution of proportions for all nine first-digits (or second digits, etc.). Similar issues arise for these variations.)

In the absence of a theoretical model for the error, I suggest that the 40 BL-suitable datasets collected by the author can be used to approximate the sampling distribution for the population, with respect to various measures of BL-conformance. For reasons stated above, mixtures are intentionally avoided in the sample. If “the population” is the set of all possible, distinct BL-suitable datasets in existence, and sampling bias was hopefully minimal when selecting 40 of those cases, then the amount of error in the sampling distribution, compared to the “known” center of the distribution, can be estimated by inspection. Applied to one possible conformance measure (“d*”), the result is seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Sampling Distribution for a Measure of BL-Non-Conformance.

The BL-non-conformance measure d^* , proposed by Cho and Gaines (2007), is relatively simple to calculate and less sensitive to sample size than the more commonly used chi-square (χ^2) measure. Other proposed methods have included Mean Absolute Deviation (from Benford’s) (Nigrini and Miller, 2009), or a measure similar to d^* proposed by Jermain (2011). For any sample dataset, its d^* is calculated as

$$(2) \quad d^* = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^9 (p_i - b_i)^2}}{1.036061},$$

where for each possible first digit i (from 1 to 9), p_i and b_i are the BL-expected versus the actually observed proportions of numbers, respectively, in the dataset beginning with that first digit. The denominator represents the maximum possible value for the numerator, if all numbers in the dataset begin with 9, and none begin with other numbers. d^* can therefore range from 0.0, if a dataset totally conforms to BL-expectations, up to 1.0, if the dataset is as non-conforming as possible.

If Figure 6 fairly approximates the sampling distribution, it shows that on a scale from total BL-conformance ($d^* = 0.00$) to total non-conformance ($d^* = 1.00$), no samples conform totally; and values up to a quarter of the way along the scale (i.e., up to $d^* = 0.25$) are not rare. Conventionally, we could use the 95th percentile ($d^* \approx 0.26$) as a cut-off value, and suggest that only samples with $d^* \geq 0.26$ should be viewed as particularly unusual, with respect to conformance. (Note that even for Benford’s cases, with its pre-mixtures, his 95th percentile is not reached until $d^* \approx 0.19$.)

If this amount of sampling error is accounted for, then many reported findings based on Benford's Law do not actually turn out to be beyond the model's error range, after all. Those who suggest using χ^2 as the conformance test instead, may not realise that this test itself *assumes* an error model: It assumes that actual counts will vary from the expected counts according to a Poisson distribution. The data in Figure 6 do not support using this (tighter) model of the error.

Similar considerations apply for tests suggested on a digit by digit basis (we will let pass the added risks due to multiple testing). Each boxplot in Figure 4 approximates the sampling distributions for the respective proportions of first digits starting 1, 2, etc. in a dataset. Once again, we see considerably more variance in these sampling distributions than generally acknowledged. Most proposed tests for single digit conformance to BL-expectations are based on the z-test. This in turn presumes an error distribution (i.e. the pattern of how sample proportions differ from expected ones) that will follow the binomial distribution. Again: the data in Figure 4 do not support that assumption.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In short, the attraction is acknowledged for basing hypothesis tests on familiar and visually simple models that appear to be backed by mathematics. However, an important caution is often overlooked: Reviewing the assumptions that underlie the model, and confirming that they apply for the test at hand. This reminder is never out of place, for even the most familiar models, because we often take them for granted. By examining how an "up and coming" test model such as Benford's is being promoted and used, it is hoped to further emphasize the importance of checking one's assumptions.

Mathematically, the phenomenon called Benford's Law appears well established; but the assumptions needed to apply it for rooting out fraud are hard to meet. That may explain the large gap between *claims* of how the law can be used for such fraud detection or how many others are using it, compared to actual, confirmable cases of people *relying* on it, in contexts (like audits) where direct follow-up and inspection, and possibly consequences for uncovered fraud, are feasible.

It is true that audit software such as ACL (ACL Services, 2012) now offer Benford-analysis capabilities for first- (or other-) digit proportions (expected versus actual proportions), and presumably many people are trying them. But hands-on practitioners' support often seems measured: Albrecht (2008) writes that the application of Benford's distribution is "only one of many computer-based fraud detection techniques that should be used" (p.3) In fact, he reveals, only three of "thousands" of Albrecht's trainees have ever actually reported uncovering a fraud specifically with Benford's.

Similarly, Buyse *et al.* (1998) present a number of computer-assisted techniques for detecting fraud, but caution that none is a magic bullet; and rather recommend scanning the data prudently with various techniques, in case side effects show up for how the fraudulent data were produced. If, for example, a company requires extra signing authority for payments made above \$10,000, a fraudulent manager may restrict writing fake checks to amounts in the eight or nine thousand dollar ranges. This may show up as "extra" 8's and 9's as first digits, according to BL—but clearly this could have been discovered without Benford's.

Readers are encouraged—just for fun—to try out a sample of Benford-suitable data, to see how well it conforms to BL. Feedback is welcome. Table 2 (following the References) shows the data sets used by the author. If some of the sites no longer work, or if a reader would like to see how the data were cleaned, and so on, please contact the author.

Acknowledgements

My sincere thanks to correspondents in my search to see how others were using Benford's law. I appreciated the insights of real-world forensic auditor David Malamed, and email responses to my queries from Leonard Mlodinow (author of *The Drunkard's Walk*), Ted Hill, Sukanto Bhattacharya, and Suzanne Sarason of Washington's Department of Financial Institutions. Also, thank you to all who attended my paper at the JSM conference and provided your feedback and encouragement.

References

- ACL Services 2009. About Benford analysis. *ACL* (Website). Retrieved from http://docs.acl.com/acl/920/index.jsp?topic=/com.acl.user_guide.help/data_analysis/c_about_benford_analysis.html
- Albrecht, C.C. 2008. Fraud and forensic accounting in a digital environment. *Brigham Young University*. Retrieved from <http://www.theifp.org/research-grants/IFP-Whitepaper-4.pdf>
- Albrecht, C.C. & Albrecht, W.S. 2002. Root out financial deception: Detect and eliminate fraud or suffer the consequences. *Journal of Accountancy*, 193(4), 30-34.
- Aldous, D. & Phan, T. 2010. When can one test an explanation? Compare and contrast Benford's Law and the Fuzzy CLT. *The American Statistician*, 64(3), 221-227.
- Benford, F. 1938. The law of anomalous numbers. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 78(4), 551-572.
- Berger, A. & Hill, T.P. 2011a. A basic theory of Benford's Law. *Probability Surveys*, 8, 1-126.
- Berger, A. & Hill, T.P. (2011b). Benford's Law strikes back: No simple explanation in sight for mathematical gem. *Mathematical Intelligencer*, 33, 85-91.
- Berton, L. 1995. He's got their number: Scholar uses math to foil financial fraud. *Wall Street Journal*, July 10.
- Bhattacharya, S., Kumar, K., & Smarandache, F. 2005. Conditional probability of actually detecting a financial fraud. A neutrosophic extension to Benford's law. *International Journal of Applied Mathematics*, 17(1), 7-14.
- Buyse, M., George, S.L., Evans, S., Geller, N.L., Ranstam, J., Scherrer, B., Lesaffre, E., Murray, G., Edler, L., Hutton, J. Colton, T., Lachenbruch, P., & Verma, B.L. 1998. The role of biostatistics in the prevention, detection and treatment of fraud in clinical trials. *Statistics in Medicine*, 18, 3435-3451.
- Cho, W.K.T. & Gaines, B.J. 2007. Breaking the (Benford's) law: Statistical fraud detection in campaign finance. *The American Statistician*, 61(3), 218-223.
- Deckert, J, Myagkov, M., & Ordeshook, PC 2011. Benford's Law and the detection of election fraud. *Political Analysis*, 19, 245-268.
- Durtschi, C., Hillison, W., & Pacini, C. 2004. The effective use of Benford's Law to assist in detecting fraud in accounting data. *Journal of Forensic Accounting*, 5, 17-34.
- Fewster, R.M. 2009. A simple explanation of Benford's Law. *The American Statistician*, 63(1), 26-32.

- Gauvrit, N. & Delahaye, J.-P. 2009. Loi de Benford générale. *Mathematics and Social Sciences*, 47(186), 5-15.
- Hill, T.P. 1998. The first digit phenomenon. *American Scientist*, 86(4), 358-363.
- Hill, T.P. 1995. A statistical derivation of the significant-digit law. *Statistical Science* 10(4), 354-363.
- Jamain, A. 2001. *Benford's Law*. Unpublished Dissertation Report, Department of Mathematics, Imperial College, London.
- Newcomb, S. 1881. Note on the frequency of use of the different digits in natural numbers. *American Journal of Mathematics*, 4(1), 39-40.
- Nigrini, M.J. (1999). I've got your number. *Journal of Accountancy*, 187(5), 79-83.
- Nigrini, M.J. & Miller, S.J. 2009. Data diagnostics using second-order tests of Benford's Law. *Auditing: A Journal of Practice and Theory*, 28(2), 305-324.
- Rodriguez, R.J. 2009. First significant digit patterns from mixtures of uniform distributions. *The American Statistician*, 58(1), 64-71.
- Scott, P. D., & Fasli, M. 2001. Benford's law: An empirical investigation and a novel explanation. *Unpublished Manuscript*. Retrieved from <http://cswww.essex.ac.uk/technical-reports/2001/CSM-349.pdf>

(Table 2 is on next page)

Table 2: Data Sources for the Author's Collected Datasets

Topics	by	Starting URL (as of Spring, 2013)
Boiling Points	(of a list of solvents)	http://wulfenite.fandm.edu/Data%20Table_27.html
Cellphones in Use	Country	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_number_of_mobile_phones_in_use
City Appointee Remuneration	Appointee	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/www.toronto.ca/ContentPages/2549852523.pdf#page=4
CO2 Emissions from Energy Consumption	Country	http://www.eia.gov/cfapps/ipdbproject/IEDIndex3.cfm?tid=90&pid=44&aid=8
Coal Consumption	Country	http://www.eia.gov/cfapps/ipdbproject/IEDIndex3.cfm?tid=1&pid=1&aid=2
Diploid Number of Chromosomes	Species	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_organisms_by_chromosome_count
Distances from NY City	U.S. Cities	http://www.mapsofworld.com/usa/distance-chart/new-york-ny.html
Electricity Consumption	Country	http://www.eia.gov/cfapps/ipdbproject/IEDIndex3.cfm?tid=2&pid=2&aid=2
Energy Consumption	U.S. state	http://www.census.gov/prod/2007pubs/08abstract/energy.pdf
Farm Cash Income	U.S. state	http://www.ers.usda.gov/data-products/farm-income-and-wealth-statistics.aspx
Farm Cash Receipts	Product Categories	http://www.census.gov/compendia/statab/cats/agriculture/farm_income_and_balance_sheet.html
Foreign Exchange Rates	Country (versus US)	http://www.census.gov/compendia/statab/cats/international_statistics.html
High Wind Damage	Weather Events, Texas	http://cees.tamui.edu/covertheborder/RISK/weather_events.xls
Housing Dept. Invoice--Expense	Account #	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/www.yorkcity.org/ContentPages/54602561.pdf#page=177
Housing Dept. Invoice--Revenue	Account #	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/www.yorkcity.org/ContentPages/54602561.pdf#page=175
Housing Units in Washington State	Jurisdiction	http://www.ofm.wa.gov/pop/april/default.asp#housing
Import/Export Data	U.S. customs district	http://www.census.gov/prod/2003pubs/02statab/foreign.pdf
Inland Waterways Lengths	Countries in Europe	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/ec.europa.eu/ContentPages/79450974.pdf#page=48
Liverpool Expense Amounts	{many 2011 records}	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/liverpool.gov.uk/ContentPages/2525899565.pdf#page=146
Meteor Crater Diameters	Name of crater (N. Amer)	http://www.unb.ca/passc/ImpactDatabase/ [Accessed by author on 8 April 2005]
NHL Players' Salaries	Player	http://www.zanran.com/q/player_salaries_baseball?filters%5Btype_html%5D=1&filters%5Btype_xs%5D=1
Oil Reserves	Country	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/my.liuc.it/ContentPages/2534461474.pdf#page=9
Packaged Food Sales	(by food category; Japan)	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/publications.gc.ca/ContentPages/2556442580.pdf#page=4
Paper Production	Country	http://www.bir.org/assets/Documents/industry/MagnaghiReport2010.pdf
People Living with HIV	Countries	http://www.unicef.org/sowc2012/pdfs/Table-4-HIV-AIDS_FINAL_102611.xls
Racehorse Prices	Lot number (at auction)	http://www.magicmillions.com.au/
Rejected Postal Ballots (EU Election 2004)	Local electoral riding UK	http://www.electoralcommission.org.uk/search?query=Postal+voting+and+proxies+by+local+authority%2Fconstituency*+at+the+European+Parliamentary+elections+2004&daat=on&isadvanced=false
shRNA Screening Experiment (Replication 2, Before)	(from library screen)	http://www.biomedcentral.com/content/supplementary/1752-0509-2-49-s1.xls
Stock Trading Volumes	Day (for over 24 years)	http://finance.yahoo.com/q/hp?s=RDS-B&a=11&b=30&c=1987&d=5&e=18&f=2012&g=d&z=66&y=133
Sunspots Numbers	{estimated counts}	ftp://ftp.ngdc.noaa.gov/STP/SOLAR_DATA/SUNSPOT_NUMBERS/INTERNATIONAL/yearly/YEARLY
Telephone lines in Use	Country	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_number_of_telephone_lines_in_use
Theater Counts	movies screened	http://www.the-numbers.com/features/TCountAll.php
Timber Production	County in California	www.dof.ca.gov/html/fs_data/STAT-ABS/documents/G27.xls
Top Canadian Companies' Assets	Company (Canadian)	http://www.theglobeandmail.com/report-on-business/rob-magazine/top-1000/2012-rankings-of-canadas-350-biggest-private-companies/article4372009/
Top Canadian Companies' Profits	Company (Canadian)	http://www.theglobeandmail.com/report-on-business/rob-magazine/top-1000/2012-rankings-of-canadas-350-biggest-private-companies/article4372009/
US Civil War Casualties	Battle name	http://americancivilwar.com/cwstats.html
US Foreign Grants&Credits	Country	http://www.census.gov/compendia/statab/cats/international_statistics.html
Votes for Conservatives 2008	Electoral riding in Canada	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Results_by_riding_for_the_Canadian_federal_election_2008
Water Polo Association Income	Income Category	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/collegiatewaterpolo.net/ContentPages/44108531.pdf#page=13
Worker Injuries in Kansas	NAIC Category	http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/www.dol.ks.gov/ContentPages/497957832.pdf#page=96